

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KANEZOUNE****FIRST NAME: GONGNET****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium.

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 13%

The author used the following software: (Word - Microsoft 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D.

1. Regarding the structure of an essay, which of the following is the correct format?

- Introduction, methods, results, and discussion.
- Introduction, results, and conclusion.
- Introduction, body, and conclusion.¹**
- Introduction, methods, results, and conclusion.

2. Regarding WHO style, which of the following propositions is correct?

- WHO style uses only British English.
- WHO style uses only American English.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*, 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 10.

- An author can choose American or British English without mixing them in the same paper.
- WHO style does not follow any single set of national practices in handling English; it uses a mix of British and American spelling.²**
3. A dissertation research process consists of four documents, but only two are usually required. Which of the following propositions is correct?
- The dissertation prospectus and the dissertation are usually required.³**
- The dissertation manuscript and the dissertation are usually required.
- The dissertation concept paper and the dissertation are usually required.
- The dissertation prospectus and the dissertation manuscript are usually required.
4. Which of the following propositions correctly describes the main parts of a dissertation prospectus?
- The dissertation prospectus includes an introduction and methods chapter.
- The dissertation prospectus consists of an introduction chapter, a literature review chapter, and a methods chapter.⁴**
- The dissertation prospectus consists of an introduction chapter, a methods chapter, a findings chapter, and a discussion chapter.

² World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, 2nd ed. (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 13.

³ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

⁴ Sampson, 10.

- The dissertation prospectus consists of an introduction chapter, a literature review chapter, a methods chapter, a findings chapter, and a discussion chapter.
5. Which of the following propositions correctly describes the main components of a dissertation?
- The dissertation includes an introduction and a methods chapter.
- The dissertation consists of an introduction chapter, a literature review chapter, and a methods chapter.
- The dissertation consists of an introduction chapter, a methods chapter, a findings chapter, and a discussion chapter.
- The dissertation consists of an introduction chapter, a literature review chapter, a methods chapter, a findings chapter, and a discussion chapter.**⁵
6. When citing a dissertation in the reference list using Turabian style (author-date), which of the examples below is the correct format?
- Navarro-Garcia, Guadalupe (2016). "Integrating Social Justice Values in Educational Leadership: A Study of African American and Black University Presidents." PhD diss., University of California, Los Angeles.
- Navarro-Garcia, Guadalupe. 2016. *"Integrating Social Justice Values in Educational Leadership: A Study of African American and Black University Presidents."* PhD diss., University of California, Los Angeles.

⁵ Sampson, 11.

Navarro-Garcia, Guadalupe. 2016. "Integrating Social Justice Values in Educational Leadership: A Study of African American and Black University Presidents." PhD diss., Los Angeles: University of California.

Navarro-Garcia, Guadalupe. 2016. "Integrating Social Justice Values in Educational Leadership: A Study of African American and Black University Presidents." PhD diss., University of California, Los Angeles.⁶

7. Which of the following examples is correct when citing a specific passage in a parenthetical citation in Turabian Style (author-date)?

(Wang 2016, 16–17)⁷

(Wang 2016: 16–17)

(Wang 2016; 16–17)

(Wang, 2016, 16–17)

8. When incorporating quotations into a text, which of the following propositions is correct?

If the quotation is four lines or less, run it into the text without quotation marks.

If the quotation is five lines or longer, set it off as a block quotation and enclose it with quotation marks.

⁶ Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 275.

⁷ Turabian, 265.

- If the quotation is four lines or less, run it into the text and enclose it in quotation marks, but do not include parenthetical citations.
- If the quotation is five lines or longer, set it off as a block quotation without quotation marks.⁸**

9. Regarding paraphrases, which of the following propositions is correct?

- The writing style used to express the author's ideas must be different from the style the author used.⁹**
- It is unnecessary to include in-text citations.
- The language used can resemble the words of the author.
- It is mandatory to use quotation marks.

10. Regarding citation requirements, which of the following questions does not provide the information required in citations?

- Who wrote or edited the text?
- What data identify the text?
- Who published the text?
- Why was the text published?¹⁰**

⁸ Turabian, 371.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*, 36.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 140.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. 2nd ed. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.